

Analysis of the Binary Mixtures Using the Reaction Between Iron(II) and Cerium(IV) Sulphate in Phosphoric Acid Medium

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Manuscript received 21 June 1977, revised 7 January 1978, accepted 17 May 1978

The reaction between iron(II) and cerium(IV) sulphate in phosphoric acid medium (6-12M) is studied potentiometrically and visually using methylene blue, thionine, azure A, azure B, azure C, toluidine blue, new methylene blue, variamine blue, ferroin, *p*-ethoxychrysoidine, *N*-phenylanthranilic acid and barium diphenylamine sulphonate as indicators. This reaction is made use for the analysis of binary mixtures of Fe(II)-Sn(II), Fe(II)-Ti(III), Fe(II)-U(IV), Fe(II)-Mo(V), Fe(II)-Fe(III) with Ce(IV) sulphate and Ce(IV)-U(VI), Ce(IV)-Mo(VI), Ce(IV)-V(V) and Ce(IV)-Cu(II) with iron(II).

THE survey of the literature reveals that the reaction between iron(II) and Ce(IV) sulphate in phosphoric acid medium is reported by Krishna Murty and Rao¹ by a visual titrimetric procedure where they have used cacotheline as indicator. In the importance of such a reaction for the differential estimation of binary mixtures, we have studied the reaction by a visual method using methylene blue, thionine, azure A, azure B, azure C, toluidine blue, new methylene blue, variamine blue, ferroin, *p*-ethoxychrysoidine, *N*-phenylanthranilic acid and barium diphenylamine sulphonate as indicators. This reaction is made use in the analysis of various sets of binary mixtures of Fe(II)-Sn(II), Fe(II)-Ti(III), Fe(II)-U(IV), Fe(II)-Mo(V), Fe(II)-Fe(III) with Ce(IV) sulphate and Ce(IV)-U(VI), Ce(IV)-Mo(VI), Ce(IV)-V(V) and Ce(IV)-Cu(II) with iron(II). The present communication deals with the details of the above procedures.

Experimental

Reagents: All the reagents used unless otherwise mentioned are of AR (BDH) grade.

Iron (II) Solution: Prepared by dissolving a known weight of Analytical Reagent Grade iron wire in analytical grade sulphuric acid and diluting the resulting solution to a known volume. The solution is standardised by titration with a standard solution of potassium dichromate.

Tin(II) Solution (0.1N) in 2N hydrochloric acid and titanium-(III) solution (0.1N) in 2N hydrochloric acid are prepared and standardised^{2,3,4}.

Uranyl acetate (0.1N) in 1N sulphuric acid is prepared and after reduction in Jones reductor is standardised according to the procedure of Pandu Ranga Rao and co-workers⁵.

Ammonium molybdate solution (0.1N) is prepared and standardised after reduction to molybdenum(V) in a mercury reductor by the method of Gopala Rao and Suryanarayana⁶.

Sodium Vanadate solution (0.1N) is prepared and standardised with standard iron(II) solution⁷.

Cerium(IV) solution (0.1N) is prepared and standardised with standard iron(II) solution⁷.

Cupric sulphate solution (0.1N) is prepared and standardised iodometrically⁸.

Iron(III) solution is prepared and standardised after its reduction to iron(II) by photochemical method⁹.

Potassium thiocyanate solution (10% W/V) is prepared.

Aqueous 0.1% solutions of methylene blue, thionine, azure A, azure B, azure C, toluidine blue, new methylene blue, variamine blue, *p*-ethoxychrysoidine, 0.2% solutions of cacotheline, barium diphenylamine sulphonate (B.D.A.S.), *N*-phenylanthranilic acid and 0.025M ferroin are prepared.

Syrupy phosphoric acid (Pro-analyst, E. Merck) is used.

Procedure: Enough syrupy phosphoric acid is taken in the titration vessel to give an overall acidity of 6-12M when diluted to 50ml and carbondioxide is passed through the contents for 10 min. Then an aliquot of the test solution and 0.2ml of each indicator is taken in the vessel and the titration is carried out with cerium (IV) sulphate or iron(II) solution to a sharp colour change of the indicator.

Analysis of binary mixtures using Ce(IV) sulphate. Mixtures of Fe(II)-Ti(III) and Fe(II)-Sn(II) :

Required volume of hydrochloric acid (1-2N for cacotheline and 4N for thiazine dyes) or sulphuric acid (5N) to get the desired acidity in a total volume of 30ml is taken in the titration vessel. Then aliquot of each reductant is taken after the passage of carbon dioxide for 10 min. The mixture is titrated with Ce(IV) sulphate after adding 0.2ml of each indicator (0.5ml of 0.025N oxalic acid¹⁰ is to be added in the case of titanium(III) chloride). When cacotheline¹¹ is used as indicator it is preferable to add the indicator near the end point as a part of it is found to be expended during the titration. After all the titanium(III) or tin(II) has reacted with Ce(IV), the thiazine dyes become blue and cacotheline becomes yellow. Now phosphoric acid is added to get the molarity of phosphoric acid 10M. Then the thiazine dyes become colourless and cacotheline will become pink with iron(II). Again the titration is further carried out with cerium(IV) sulphate to the sharp colour change of the indicator. The first titre value of Ce(IV) gives the corresponding amount of Ti(III) or Sn(II). The difference between the titre values of Ce(IV) corresponding to the second and first equivalence points gives the amount of Fe(II) present in the mixture. Typical results are given in Table-1.

Mixtures of Fe(II)-U(IV) and Fe(II)-Mo(V) : In one aliquot the amount of Fe(II) is determined in phosphoric acid medium as given above. In a second aliquot the total amount of Fe(II) and U(IV) is determined under the conditions given by Birnbaum and Edmonds¹² for the estimation of U(IV) with ceric sulphate. Similarly the total amount of Fe(II) and Mo(V) is determined by the method of Furman and Murray¹³ for the estimation of Mo(V) with ceric sulphate. From the results, the amount of U(IV) and Mo(V) can be computed. Typical results are given in Table 1.

Mixture of Fe(II)-Fe(III) : In one aliquot, Fe(II) is determined as described above. In another aliquot the total of Fe(II)+Fe(III) is determined after Fe(III) is reduced to Fe(II) by photochemical method⁹. By subtracting the amount of iron(II) obtained in the first case from that in the second case the amount of Fe(III) is obtained. Typical results are given in Table 1.

Analysis of binary mixtures using iron (II) :

Mixtures of Ce(IV)-U(VI), Ce(IV)-Mo(VI) and Ce(IV)-Cu(II) :

Required volume of phosphoric acid is taken in the titration vessel to get the acidity of 8M. Then aliquots of Ce(IV) and U(VI) or Mo(VI), or Cu(II) are taken together with 0.2ml of N-phenylanthranilic acid or B.D.A.S. as indicator. The contents are titrated with iron(II) while passing carbon dioxide. At the first equivalence point the indicator becomes colourless. Then the molarity of the phosphoric acid is raised to 12M (in the case of copper(II) 10M H₃PO₄ concentration and 0.5ml of 10% KCNS) and the titration is continued with iron(II) by adding any of the thiazine dyes mentioned above or cacotheline¹⁴ to the sharp colour change. The former titre of iron(II) corresponds to the amount of Ce(IV) where as the difference of the two titre values of iron(II) corresponds to the amount of U(VI) or Mo(VI) or Cu(II). Typical results are given in Table 2.

Mixture of Ce(IV)-V(V) : Required volume of phosphoric acid is taken in the titration vessel to get the acidity of 8M. Then aliquots of Ce(IV) and V(V) are taken together with N-phenylanthranilic acid as indicator. The contents are titrated with iron(II) while passing carbon dioxide. At the end point the indicator becomes colourless and the titre value of iron(II) gives the total amount of Ce(IV) and V(V). Now the molarity of phosphoric acid

TABLE-1 DIFFERENTIAL ANALYSIS OF THE MIXTURES OF Fe(II)-SN(II), Fe(II)-TI(III), Fe(II)-U(IV), Fe(II)-MO(V) AND Fe(II)-Fe(III) WITH CERIUM(IV) SULPHATE.

Amount taken mg. Fe(II) + Sn(II)	Amount of Fe(II) found mg.	Standard Deviation	% Error	Amount of Sn(II) found mg.	Standard Deviation	% Error
2.88 + 10.38	2.88	0.000	0.00	10.35	0.015	0.29
11.53 + 20.75	11.49	0.028	0.35	20.75	0.013	0.00
23.06 + 41.49	22.97	0.025	0.39	41.40	0.019	0.22
Fe(II) + Ti(III)				Ti(III)		
5.68 + 3.85	5.663	0.009	0.41	3.84	0.008	0.29
11.37 + 7.71	11.33	0.013	0.35	7.68	0.011	0.31
22.74 + 15.42	22.70	0.028	0.18	15.38	0.016	0.26
Fe(II) + U(IV)				U(IV)		
5.74 + 17.80	5.73	0.021	0.19	17.80	0.019	0.00
14.35 + 44.49	14.29	0.026	0.42	44.61	0.028	0.27
22.96 + 71.19	22.88	0.033	0.35	71.29	0.039	0.14
Fe(II) + Mo(V)				Mo(V)		
5.72 + 11.73	5.70	0.016	0.33	11.77	0.016	0.34
11.44 + 23.51	11.40	0.029	0.35	23.54	0.023	0.13
17.16 + 35.28	17.09	0.021	0.41	35.35	0.036	0.20
Fe(II) + Fe(III)				Fe(III)		
5.70 + 26.20	5.68	0.021	0.39	26.12	0.028	0.31
17.10 + 11.40	17.03	0.000	0.41	11.37	0.022	0.26
23.50 + 5.998	23.44	0.039	0.26	5.982	0.013	0.27

TABLE-2 DIFFERENTIAL ANALYSIS OF THE MIXTURES OF Ce(IV)-U(VI), Ce(IV)-Mo(VI), Ce(IV)-V(V) AND Ce(IV)-Cu(II) WITH IRON(II).

Amount taken mg. Ce(IV) + U(VI)	Amount of Ce(IV) found mg.	Standard Deviation	% Error	Amount U(VI) found mg.	Standard Deviation	% Error
5.63+12.45	5.63	0.025	0.00	12.45	0.047	0.00
15.48+27.40	15.53	0.035	0.32	27.25	0.018	0.18
28.14+49.80	28.02	0.043	0.43	49.91	0.042	0.04
Ce(IV) + Mo(VI)				Mo(VI)		
8.44+ 5.68	8.467	0.000	0.32	5.69	0.017	0.26
30.95+28.30	31.01	0.070	0.19	28.23	0.029	0.25
56.27+58.02	56.22	0.035	0.09	57.92	0.034	0.17
Ce(IV) + V(V)				V(V)		
11.26+ 3.99	11.23	0.025	0.27	3.99	0.008	0.00
26.73+11.27	26.71	0.065	0.07	11.24	0.010	0.27
42.20+16.90	42.29	0.061	0.21	16.87	0.009	0.18
Ce(IV) + Cu(II)				Cu(II)		
29.55+11.48	29.48	0.030	0.24	11.52	0.011	0.35
56.28+23.54	56.21	0.000	0.12	23.51	0.015	0.13
77.39+31.58	77.44	0.049	0.06	31.54	0.023	0.13

is raised to 12M and the titration is further continued with iron(II) by adding any of the thiazine dyes or cacotheleine¹⁴ as indicator to the sharp colour change. In the second stage the formed V(IV) from V(V) during the former titration with iron(II) is reduced to V(III). Thus the second titre value of iron(II) consumed corresponding to V(IV) gives the amount of V(V) in the mixture on calculation. Typical results are given in Table 2.

Discussion

The reaction between iron(II) and Ce(IV) sulphate in phosphoric acid medium has the advantage that oxalate, tartrate, citrate, As(III), U(IV), Hg(II), Mo(V) and chloride do not interfere when the thiazine dyes are used as indicators. Oxalate, As(III), U(IV) and Mo(V) interfere in the estimation of Fe(II) with Ce(IV) sulphate in sulphuric acid medium.

In the light of the application of the reaction for the analysis of many binary mixtures we have studied the reaction between Ce(IV) and iron(II) in phosphoric acid medium also through a potentiometric end point. In both the cases of direct and reverse potentiometric titrations in 6-12M phosphoric acid medium, steady potentials are attained immediately throughout the titration and quantitative results are obtained. In the analysis of the above said binary mixtures in which cerium(IV) is a common constituent with U(VI), Mo(VI), V(V) and Cu(II), differential potentiometric titrations are also done in phosphoric acid medium. In the estimation of Ce(IV) with iron(II) in the first titration, the phosphoric acid concentration should be maintained at 7-8M where as in the second titration in the estimation of U(VI), Mo(VI) and V(IV) with iron(II) the concentration of phosphoric acid is to be raised to 12M. In the second part of the titration of mixtures, U(VI), Mo(VI), V(IV) and Cu(II) are determined according to the established procedures¹⁵⁻¹⁸.

Acknowledgement

One of us (V.S.N.) gratefully acknowledges the C.S.I.R. for the award of Senior Research Fellowship.

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